

Connecting Dots: Creating a Bridge Between Phenotypic Data Collection Tools and ARC using BrAPI

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Abstract

This research stay report delineates the development and implementation of a novel tool, called brapi2arc, which has been developed with the objective of facilitating the submission of phenotypic data collected through mobile apps like GridScore using the Breeding API (BrAPI) standard to an Annotated Research Context (ARC). Our solution addresses the need for standardized data exchange between app-based phenotyping platforms and structured research environments. By leveraging the BrAPI standard, we facilitate seamless interoperability between phenotypic data collection applications and Annotated Research Contexts (ARCs), thereby enabling efficient data integration. The tool automates the conversion of raw app data into standardized data formats, thereby ensuring data consistency and quality. Through testing and validation, we demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach in facilitating seamless data flow between GridScore and an ARC. This implementation contributes to advancing phenomic research by enhancing data accessibility, reducing manual entry errors, and promoting interoperability across different platforms and tools in plant breeding research.

Keywords: BrAPI, Plant Phenotyping, ETL, ARC

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the field of plant breeding research has witnessed considerable advances in technology-driven methodologies for data collection and analysis. Mobile applications for collecting phenotypic data, such as GridScore [2], have gained traction among researchers. These apps offer a number of advantages over traditional data collection methods, including:

- 1. Reduced error potential:** They minimize the impact of human factors like handwriting errors and typos, which were common in paper-based recording systems.
- 2. Improved efficiency:** Automated data entry reduces time spent on manual transcription, allowing researchers to focus more on experimental design and analysis.
- 3. Real-time data capture:** Researchers can immediately record observations, reducing the likelihood of forgetting important details.
- 4. Integration capabilities:** Several of these apps now incorporate Breeding API (BrAPI) interfaces [1], facilitating easier connections with other research tools and databases.

Despite these advantages, the introduction of the Annotated Research Context (ARC) data structure [3] has given rise to a new challenge. The Annotated Research Context (ARC) data structure provides a powerful framework for version-controlled creation and storage of research datasets, offering enhanced data management and collaboration features. However, the existing disparity between app-based phenotyping platforms and ARCs has constrained their broad deployment in plant breeding research.

To address this limitation, we have developed the brapi2arc tool. This innovative solution serves as a converter between mobile apps like GridScore and ARCs, thereby addressing the need for standardized data exchange between app-based phenotyping platforms and structured research environments. By leveraging the BrAPI standard, the brapi2arc tool facilitates seamless interoperability between phenotypic data collection applications and Annotated Research Contexts (ARCs). This tool automates the conversion of raw app data into standardized data formats, thereby ensuring data consistency and

quality. The effectiveness of our approach in facilitating a smooth data flow between GridScore and an ARC was demonstrated through testing. This implementation contributes significantly to advancing phenomic research by enhancing data accessibility, reducing manual entry errors, and promoting interoperability across different platforms and tools in plant breeding research.

In what follows, the details of the brapi2arc tool will be presented, including its development process, testing methodology, and the implications of this innovation for the field of plant breeding research.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Tool Development

The brapi2arc tool is a BrAPI server that is available as a Docker image. It enables the user to populate an ARC that is available in a DataHUB with phenotypic observation data. The BrAPI server was implemented in Python 3.11 and utilizes the Litestar framework, version 2.8.3. During the initialization of the application, the ARC is retrieved from the DataHUB, and the ARCctrl library [7], version 2.0.0a2, is employed to facilitate the interconversion between JSON, XLSX, and RO-Crate serializations of the dataset.

The BrAPI interfaces facilitate the retrieval of the basic data from the ARC, thereby enabling the implementation of validation logic within the phenotyping application. Moreover, the selected search endpoints and the interfaces for creating observation units, as well as the observations themselves, are made possible.

2.2. Test Datasets

To assess the operational efficacy of brapi2arc, two data sets were transferred to the ARC structure. Two workflows are supported by brapi2arc, and thus a study with and without a study design was created for each data set.

The first data set [5] is an artificially generated data set for potatoes. It has two observation variables with flower color and plants alive. The original dataset is used in GridScore as a showcase for timeline trials. The ARC was generated and stored in the DataHUB.

The second data set [4] is a barley trial focussing on date-type obser-

Figure 1. Sequence diagram of both supported workflows of brapi2arc. Either the study design part of the import or export.

71 vation variables. It has in total five observation variables including
 72 Awn Tipping, Heading, Maturity, Plant height and Row type. The
 73 original dataset is used in GridScore as a showcase for trials with
 74 date-type traits. The ARC was generated and stored in the DataHUB.

75 **3. Results**

76 The testing of brapi2arc’s functionality was based on the described
 77 data sets in conjunction with GridScore. The functionality of this
 78 application is discussed in the following section. The workflow for
 79 other data collection applications may be adapted, but it is likely to
 80 be similar.

81 As brapi2arc creates commits to the ARC, it is necessary to create a
 82 personal access token in the DataHUB independently of the data col-
 83 lection application. This is sent in the BrAPI calls as an authorization
 84 bearer token, which allows brapi2arc to authenticate itself against
 85 the REST API of the DataHUB.

86 **3.1. Using Existing Study Design**

87 In the first workflow, the study design is pre-stored in the ARC. This
 88 entails that the location and the entry type (check versus test) of the
 89 observation units have already been defined. Consequently, the initial

90 step is to import the data from the ARC into GridScore. To achieve
 91 this, the BrAPI parameters for brapi2arc can be entered in GridScore
 92 in the BrAPI Trial Import, after which the corresponding study can
 93 be loaded. The user must then import the observation variables. The
 94 BrAPI settings are remembered by GridScore from the previous step.
 95 At this point, the user can begin recording the observations. Finally,
 96 the user can write the data back to the ARC via the BrAPI export.

97 **3.2. Creating New Study Design**

98 As an alternative, the study design can be submitted to the ARC via
 99 GridScore. It is presumed that the specific germplasm to be utilized
 100 in the experiment has already been determined. These have already
 101 been made available in the ARC; however, the observation units,
 102 along with their respective locations and entry types, have yet to
 103 be documented. To accomplish this, the user is first required to
 104 create the trial in GridScore. The user may elect to load either the
 105 Timeline trial or the Barley trial for testing purposes. Subsequently,
 106 the observations can be recorded. The observations have already been
 107 created for the test data sets. Two additional lookups are incorporated
 108 into the final stages of the BrAPI export. Firstly, it is necessary to
 109 ensure that a germplasm is available in the ARC for each observation
 110 unit. Secondly, it is necessary to ensure that the observation variables
 111 are available. The export is then executed in the usual manner.

112 **4. Discussion**

113 The brapi2arc tool has been developed as a significant component of
 114 the toolkit for utilising ARCs. It permits the immediate linkage of a
 115 phenotypic data collection application with the ARC. One challenge
 116 associated with tools such as the MIAPPE Wizard [6] is to facilitate
 117 the input of observations in a generic and straightforward manner.
 118 This necessitates the utilisation of templates or subsequent mapping
 119 of the information by the user. Both approaches have inherent lim-
 120 itations. While templates facilitate implementation, they shift the
 121 primary responsibility to the user, who must first transform their
 122 data into the specified format, including potential misuses and er-
 123 rors. In contrast, information mapping offers a more flexible solution.
 124 However, erroneous entries may also occur, or the format may be
 125 incompatible with the input mask. Data collection applications, in
 126 contrast, address these issues by incorporating basic input control
 127 and mapping the data to their own data schema from the moment it
 128 is collected. Consequently, the mapping of the data is no longer the
 129 responsibility of the user, but is instead automated.

130 The brapi2arc tool thus offers a substantial enhancement to the ca-
 131 pabilities of ARCs, yet it is not designed to supplant existing tools
 132 such as the MIAPPE Wizard. Instead, it is meant to be employed
 133 in conjunction with such tools. The user can utilize the MIAPPE
 134 Wizard to set up and create the ARC, store it in the DataHUB, and
 135 then employ brapi2arc together with tools such as GridScore to store
 136 the actual results of the phenotypic experiment.

137 **Code availability**

138 All outputs are made publically available. The code for brapi2arc is
 139 hosted at <https://github.com/IPK-BIT/brapi2arc>, the datasets used for
 140 testing can be found at <https://git.nfdi4plants.org/feser/jhi-test-data>
 141 and <https://git.nfdi4plants.org/feser/jhi-barley-trial>. Documentation
 142 is found at <https://brapi2arc.rtfd.io/en/latest>. The docker image is
 143 available through <https://ghcr.io/ipk-bit/brapi2arc>.

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